

EMPOWERMENT OF TECHNOPRENEURSHIP ON SMALL-MEDIUM INDUSTRY THROUGH THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY E-COMMERCE BASED ECONOMIC KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract

Generally there are three main reasons underlying the importance of the existence and development of micro small medium enterprises (MSME); (1) MSME has a performance that tends to be better in terms of producing a productive workforce; (2) MSME is as part of its dynamics, MSME often achieves increased productivity through investment and technological change; and (3) MSME has advantages in terms of flexibility compared to large scale enterprises. In addition, MSME in Indonesia has played an important role especially in employment, increasing the number of business units, and supporting household income. Seeing the role of MSME that is strategic for economic growth and industry in Indonesia, it is necessary to be mobilized and developed because of its great potential in encouraging the economic growth of the community and at the same time becomes the source of income for most people in improving their welfare. So far, MSME *Ariny batik* is engaged in conventional clothing in the conventional way, so the marketing process looks less than the maximum because it only has a coverage area that is not too broad. Based on the conditions and situations experienced by *Ariny batik*, it is needed to be revamped from the marketing sector by utilizing e-commerce system. Where, e-commerce is an activity of buying and or selling goods and services electronically through the Internet network. It is by way of training and creating a web-based e-commerce system. The training aims to increase sales turnover from *Ariny batik*. Methods conducted are in forms of location survey, problem formulation, e-commerce training, creation system, testing system, implementation system, and evaluation.

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1. Introduction

Micro small medium enterprises (MSME) is the backbone in increasing the economic growth and industry of a country. Almost 90% of the total business in the world is the contribution of MSME, hence many countries appreciate the existence of MSME including Indonesia. Generally, there are three main reasons underlying the importance of the existence and development of SMEs; (1) MSME has a performance that tend to be better in terms of producing a productive workforce, (2) MSME is as part of its dynamics, it often

achieves increased productivity through investment and technological change; and (3) MSME has advantages in terms of flexibility compared to large scale enterprises. In addition, MSME in Indonesia has played an important role especially in employment, increasing the number of business units, and supporting household income.

Seeing the role of MSME that is strategic for economic growth and industry in Indonesia, it is necessary to be mobilized and developed because of its great potential in encouraging the economic growth of the community and at the same time become the source of income of most people in improving their welfare.

In Jambi Province, there are at least 81,959 MSME. It consists of 11 regencies and cities in Jambi Province. From the 11 regencies and cities, most are *Muaro Jambi* with a total of 22,560, followed by the Jambi city with a total of 13,723 businesses, then *Sungai Penuh* as 13.309 and *Tanjabbar* as 12.309. While for other districts followed, there is a few in *Batanghari*, that is 394 business (Muzakir, 2016). So far, MSMEs in Jambi Province only market their products conventionally, so the sales turnover decreased dramatically. If the sales cycle is still ongoing, it is likely that MSME will be out of business. Whereas, the perpetrators of MSME are very keen to expand its marketing to other areas, because constrained funds for promotion then the desire has not been realized until now.

If the marketing of products can expand, then it will be able to increase purchasing power so that automatic production increases and this will bring prosperity to the community of MSME perpetrators. MSME in Jambi Province is increasingly threatened by high free marketing competition since early 2016. In average, MSMEs which are difficult to compete eventually have to go out of business due to not able to sell some processed products themselves. This is due to productivity until the management of some MSME is still low, some of them are not active (Kurniawan, 2016)

If related to the development of ICT (information and communication technology) today, it can be seen that many perpetrators of MSME in Jambi who have not utilized ICT support in running their business. Based on the conditions and situations experienced by the partners it is necessary carried out revamping of the marketing sector by utilizing e-commerce system. Meanwhile, e-commerce is an activity of buying/selling goods and services electronically through the Internet network. In addition, it can do the best sales and service by using a 24-hour online store for its customers.

Electronic commerce or e-commerce, is an important part of the development of technology in the world of internet. The use of e-commerce system is very beneficial to many parties; consumers, producers and sellers. For the consumers, using e-commerce can save time and cost. No need to linger queue to get a good or service desired. Additionally, the latest prices can be obtained and may be the price of goods or services offered through e-commerce, they can be cheaper than the price through intermediaries both agents and stores, because the distribution of goods and services from producers to consumers shorter than the provider goods and services. Therefore, MSME should be using ICT in accordance with the level of MSME. Without this, it is believed MSME will remain weak compared to big companies in terms of marketing, trade, managerial skills, and so on. A key factor in the importance of using e-commerce systems to MSME is the increased ability to get customer feedback in a timely manner other than cost savings and marketing

expansions. In the context of marketing, with e-commerce systems, businesses that run small-scale can also penetrate both domestic and global market.

So far, MSME *Ariny Batik* marketing is still using conventional way, so the marketing process looks less than the maximum because it only has a coverage area that is not too broad. For that need to be done through e-commerce as an alternative, for more maximum marketing and efficient and has a wider coverage area. In addition, consumers have the flexibility in choosing an item and save their time in buying goods.

2. Partner Problems

Based on the analysis of the situation arises in MSME *Ariny Batik*, the problems are; 1) the perpetrators of MSME *Ariny Batik* in Jambi city only markets its products conventionally, 2) difficulty in promoting products of MSME *Ariny Batik* because it requires a considerable cost, 3) lack of access to capital, access to technology and information, market access and marketing, access to human resource professionalism, and company management. Problems in the traditional marketing of MSME *Ariny Batik* need to get priority scale especially in terms of promotion, because this problem is a fundamental problem that determines the sustainability and development of MSME *Ariny Batik*.

3. Method of Implementation

Implementation Procedures

Method of implementation of activities to find solutions of marketing problems in MSME *Ariny Batik* carried out with working procedures that supports the realization of making this system. Working procedures can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Implementation Procedures

Location of Survey

Survey of MSME locations to list products to be marketed. The data collection include product type, product price, product photos, MSME address, phone number (can be contacted).

Formulation of Problem

After obtaining data from each MSME, then the next step is to formulate the problems gained from complaints of each MSME. The complaints include; the marketing area carried out only in the local area, and products are less widely known.

E-commerce Training

The importance of socialization is to market MSME results, then to conduct organized, structured and sustainable training to partners on how to use and utilize E-Commerce.

Creation System

Designing a website contains the profile of MSME *Ariny Batik* and the resulting product as well as designing e-commerce in the website.

Test System

The system that has been made is tested for feasibility in marketing every product of MSME *Ariny Batik*.

Implementation System

The main purpose of the program is to provide marketing tools to MSME by using a web portal and accessed via internet. This web will provide an unlimited marketing means of space and time. In the products appeared in the web portal, there will be a column to display the address and contact owners of MSME.

In this portal, there are two transaction models. First, buyers can directly interact with MSME owners by meeting directly or contacting contact owner of MSME. In this transaction, model can be in nego process until a price agreement arises. The second transaction model is using a partner account facility (retra). In this transaction model, the buyer can directly order the goods through the existing facilities in the web portal. After that, the buyer can directly transfer to retra with nominal that has been listed on web portal. After the buyer transfers money, the goods will be directly sent by owners of MSME. Money will be given to MSME owners if the goods ordered have been received by the buyer. If the MSME owner does not deliver the order, the money will be returned to the buyer.

4. Evaluation

Evaluation activities are conducted to obtain a real picture on the impact of the use of technology that has been applied simultaneously to measure the success rate of program implementation of community service activities. In addition, there is also indirect assistance (monitoring and communication) in order to obtain maximum results and maintain the sustainability of the technology used.

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